

Heterosis Studies for Yield and Yield Component Traits in Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.)

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Abstract

In the present investigation, information on the magnitude of heterosis was obtained for seed yield per plant and its related components following line x tester mating design involving four lines and seven testers of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.). The eleven parents and their 28 F₁s with two standard checks were tested for fourteen characters Niger Research Station, Vanarasi in a randomized block design with three replications. The magnitude of non-additive variance was higher for seed yield per plant and its contributing traits indicating the predominant role of non-additive gene action in the inheritance of the traits. The maximum value of standard heterosis for seed yield per plant was observed for SVCMS-4 x SVSR-5 followed by SVCMS-2 x SVSR-3, SVCMS-4 x SVSR-4, SVSH-3 x SVSH-5 and SVSH-2 x SVSH-5. The high heterotic response in these hybrids for seed yield per plant resulted mainly due to substantial heterosis for head diameter, 100 seed weight and seed volume weight.

Key Words: Sunflower, Heterosis, Yield

Introduction

Sunflower is highly cross pollinated crop and the main objective of sunflower breeding is to develop high yielding hybrid cultivars with stable and high yield through exploitation of heterosis. Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) is the fourth important oilseed crop in the world next to soybean, groundnut and rapeseed. It belongs to the genus *Helianthus*, family Asteraceae, tribe Heliantheae, sub-tribe Helianthae which includes 20 genera with 400 sub-species, originated in USA (Heiser, 1978). It has 2n=34 and cross pollinated in nature. Sunflower, being a highly cross-pollinated crop is ideally suited for exploitation of heterosis. Commercial exploitation of heterosis has been possible using cytoplasmic male sterility- restorer system.

However, commercial cultivation in India started with open pollinated varieties like EC 68414 (Peredovik), EC 68415 (Armaviriski, 3497) and Morden (Cermianka-66). Heterosis breeding has evolved successfully in sunflower breeding ever since the discovery of first cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS) source by Leclercq (1969) from the interspecific cross *H. petiolaris* Nutt, x *H. annuus* and fertility restoration by Kinman (1970) that gave the required momentum for commercial hybrid seed production in sunflower using CMS source.

In heterosis breeding, the selection of parents or inbreds with good combining ability is very important in producing superior hybrids. The estimation of general combining ability (GCA) and specific combining ability (SCA) helps in identifying the potential parents in the production of superior hybrids for seed yield and oil content. It is useful in knowing the type of gene action controlling various characters and development of suitable breeding strategies. The line x tester analysis (Kempthorne, 1957) is one of the simplest and efficient method of evaluating large number of inbreds for combining ability and *per se* performance. Thus, this investigation was undertaken to determine magnitude of heterosis for yield and other quantitative traits using L x T mating design.

Materials and Methods

In the present study 28 hybrids obtained by adopting line x tester mating design consisted 4 lines (SVCMS-1, SVCMS-2, SVCMS-3 and SVCMS-4) and 7 testers (SVSR-1, SVSR-2, SVSR-3, SVSR-4, SVSR-5, SVSR-6 and SVSR-7) along with two checks *viz.*, Phule Raviraj and LSFH-171 were evaluated in randomized block design with three replication and tested at Niger Research Station, Vanarasi (NAU, Navasari) during *rabi* 2019-20. The performance of different hybrids, parents and checks in respect to eleven characters was studied for estimating the stability and significance of genotype environment interactions. Each hybrid was represented by single Rows of 3.0 m length with 60 x 30 cm spacing between and within rows, respectively. Observations were recorded in each entries on randomly selected five plants for six characters *viz.*, days to 50 per cent flowering, days to physiological maturity, head diameter (cm), seed yield per plant (g), 100 grain weight and seed volume weight (g/100 ml). The analysis was carried out in computer using software INDOSTAT as per standard method of line x tester in order to estimate gca, sca effect at individual location and pooled analysis along with heterosis study for each genotype.

Results and discussion

Heterosis

Heterosis is the measure of deviation of progeny means from parental means. For exploitation of hybrid vigour, high degree of heterosis for yield and its components is a prerequisite in crop improvement programme. The negative heterosis is also important for characters *viz*; flowering, maturity and plant height in sunflower. In the present investigation two

types of heterosis *viz*; heterobeltiosis or better parent heterosis and standard or economic heterosis have been studied. Major objectives of the present study were to identify promising hybrids which may give high degree of useful (economic) heterosis.

The magnitude of heterosis over better parent ranged from 2.83 % (SVCMS-3 x SVSR-7) to 18.36 % (SVCMS-3 x SVSR-1) and the range of economic heterosis over the best check were -9.17 % (SVCMS-3 x SVSR-7) to 3.75 % (SVCMS-3 x SVSR-5) for 50 % flowering. For days to maturity the range of heterobeltiosis was found to be between 3.35 % (SVCMS-1 x SVSR-6) to 13.89 % (SVCMS-2 x SVSR-3) and the quantum of standard heterosis ranged from -3.17 % (SVCMS-1 x SVSR-3) to 6.34 % (SVCMS-2 x SVSR-3). This findings similar to Karasu *et al.* (2010), Neelima and Rafi (2013) and Lakshman *et al.* (2020).

The range of heterobeltiosis for head diameter was from 1.77 % (SVCMS-1 x SVSR-3) to 83.92 % (SVCMS-4 x SVSR-5). Among the 28 hybrids, 25 hybrids showed significant positive better parent heterosis and 4 hybrids showed significant positive standard heterosis over best check LSFH-171. The magnitude of heterobeltiosis for seed yield per plant ranged from 53.81 % (SVCMS-1 x SVSR-5) to 136.9 % (SVCMS-4 x SVSR-5), while the standard heterosis ranged from -9.62 % (SVCMS-3 x SVSR-2) to 40.61 % (SVCMS-4 x SVSR-5) over check LSFH-171. Among the 28 hybrids, all the hybrids showed significant positive better parent heterosis and 5 hybrids showed significant positive standard heterosis over best check LSFH-171. The presence of significant positive heterosis in determining for above traits has been reported Siddiqui and Baig (2000), Phad *et al.* (2002), Sakthivel (2003), Raghavendra (2004), Uttam *et al.* (2005), Rao (2006), Thombare *et al.* (2007), Sawargaonkar and Ghodke (2008), Dudhe *et al.* (2009), Sujata and Reddy (2009), Datta *et al.* (2011), Rathi *et al.* (2016) and Dhootmal (2017) and Lakshman *et al.* (2020).

The spectrum of variation for heterobeltiosis for seed volume weight ranged from -15.66 % (SVCMS-1 x SVSR-3) to 52.56 % (SVCMS-3 x SVSR-6) and for standard heterosis ranged from -9.64 % (SVCMS-1 x SVSR-5) to 13.66 % (SVCMS-4 x SVSR-5) over best check LSFH-171. The maximum heterosis percentage over standard check LSFH-171 for 100 seed weight was displayed by the crosses SVCMS-4 x SVSR-5 (25.43 %); SVCMS-2 x SVSR-3 (24.28 %); SVCMS-2 x SVSR-5 (15.03 %) and SVCMS-3 x SVSR-5 (14.45 %) significant positive direction. This result similar to Sassikumar and Gopalan (2000), Bajaj *et al.* (2003), Khan *et al.* (2004), Karasu *et al.* (2010), Neelima and Raffi (2013) and Bhoite *et al.* (2018).

Based on the per se performance and extent of heterosis, five best crosses viz., SVCMS-2 x SVSR-3, SVCMS-2 x SVSR-5, SVCMS-3 x SVSR-5 SVCMS-4 x SVSR-4 and SVCMS-4 x SVSR-5 possess good seed yield per plant over best check LSFH-171. These better performing crosses can be used for exploiting hybrid vigour and need to be evaluated for stability parameter.

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Table 4.4.1.1: ANOVA for combining ability for days to 50% flowering, days to maturity and plant height (cm) under individual location and in pooled over locations

Source	d.f.	Days to 50% flowering	Days to maturity
		E3	E3
		Vanarasi	Vanarasi
Replicates	2	6.333	4.333
Hybrids	27	22.823**	33.136**
Line	3	4.488	21.365
Tester	6	38.468	33.944
Line x Tester	1	20.664*	34.828**
Error	54	9.864	10.062

* and ** Significant at 5 % and 1 % level of probability, respectively

Table 4.4.1.2: ANOVA for combining ability for head diameter (cm), seed filling (%) and hull content (%) under individual and pooled over environments

Source	d.f.	Head diameter (cm)
		E3
		Vanarasi
Replicates	2	2.153
Hybrids	27	20.112**
Line	3	23.881
Tester	6	26.149
Line x Tester	1	17.471**
Error	54	1.556

Table 4.4.1.3: ANOVA for combining ability for seed yield per plant (g), 100 grain weight (g) and seed volume weight (g/100 ml) under individual and pooled over environments

Source	d.f.	Seed yield per plant (g)	100 grain weight (g)	Seed volume weight (g/100 ml)
		E3	E3	E3
		Vanarasi	Vanarasi	Vanarasi
Replicates	2	4.79	0.058	1.681
Hybrids	27	79.446**	0.954**	17.092**
Line	3	93.922	1.047	20.622
Tester	6	113.378	1.507	22.33
Line x Tester	1	65.722**	0.754**	14.758**
Error	54	25.264	0.223	3.753

* and ** Significant at 5 % and 1 % level of probability, respectively

Table 4.3.1 Estimates of heterosis over better parent (BP) and standard check (SC) under individual and pooled over environments for days to 50 per cent flowering in sunflower

Sr. No.	Crosses	Days to 50 per cent flowering	
		Vanarasi (E ₃)	
		BP	SC
1	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-1	11.79**	-1.25
2	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-2	12.26**	-0.83
3	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-3	8.80*	-2.08
4	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-4	12.90**	2.08
5	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-5	4.67	-6.67
6	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-6	9.43*	-3.33
7	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-7	16.04**	2.5
8	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-1	6.54	-5
9	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-2	5.14	-6.25
10	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-3	12.04**	0.83
11	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-4	10.14*	-0.42
12	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-5	12.62**	0.42
13	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-6	7.48	-4.17
14	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-7	7.01	-4.58
15	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-1	18.36**	2.08
16	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-2	15.31**	-5.83
17	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-3	11.57**	0.42
18	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-4	9.22*	-1.25
19	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-5	16.36**	3.75
20	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-6	7.08	-5.42
21	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-7	2.83	-9.17*
22	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-1	11.43**	-2.5
23	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-2	7.14	-6.25
24	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-3	13.89**	2.5
25	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-4	11.06**	0.42
26	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-5	13.55**	1.25
27	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-6	10.38*	-2.5
28	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-7	6.6	-5.83
	S.E.(d) ±	2.49	2.875
	CD @ 5%	4.992	5.765

*, ** Significant at 5 and 1 per cent probability levels, respectively.

BP, SC indicates better parent and standard check LSFH-171, respectively.

Table 4.3.2 Estimates of heterosis over better parent (BP) and standard check (SC) under individual and pooled over environments for days to maturity in sunflower

Sr. No.	Crosses	Days to maturity	
		Vanarasi (E ₃)	
		BP	SC
1	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-1	6.77**	0
2	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-2	8.92**	2.02
3	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-3	3.38	-3.17
4	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-4	10.77**	3.75
5	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-5	4.31	-2.31
6	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-6	3.35	-2.31
7	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-7	11.93**	5.48*
8	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-1	8.02**	0.86
9	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-2	6.17*	-0.86
10	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-3	13.89**	6.34**
11	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-4	11.11**	3.75
12	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-5	11.73**	4.32
13	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-6	6.40*	0.58
14	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-7	4.59	-1.44
15	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-1	12.54**	3.46
16	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-2	6.98**	-2.88
17	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-3	11.56**	2.88
18	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-4	9.09**	0.29
19	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-5	13.40**	4.90*
20	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-6	6.10*	0.29
21	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-7	3.67	-2.31
22	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-1	10.53**	2.88
23	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-2	6.81**	-0.58
24	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-3	11.76**	4.03
25	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-4	11.76**	4.03
26	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-5	12.38**	4.61
27	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-6	9.45**	3.46
28	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-7	4.28	-1.73
	S.E.(d) ±	2.327	2.687
	CD @ 5%	4.666	5.388

*, ** Significant at 5 and 1 per cent probability levels, respectively.

BP, SC indicates better parent and standard check LSFH-171, respectively

Table 4.3.4 Estimates of heterosis over better parent (BP) and standard check (SC) under individual and pooled over environments for head diameter (cm) in sunflower

Sr. No.	Crosses	Head diameter (cm)	
		Vanarasi (E ₃)	
		BP	SC
1	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-1	38.22**	-6.88
2	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-2	52.70**	-1.36
3	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-3	1.77	-23.96**
4	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-4	41.09**	3.19
5	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-5	13.18	-23.85**
6	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-6	22.93**	-12.25*
7	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-7	69.96**	4.76
8	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-1	46.46**	-1.33
9	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-2	15.62	-23.39**
10	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-3	57.53**	17.69**
11	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-4	38.98**	1.65
12	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-5	53.85**	3.51
13	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-6	46.76**	4.76
14	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-7	44.32**	-4.37
15	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-1	61.24**	8.63
16	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-2	17.55*	-24.07**
17	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-3	37.78**	2.94
18	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-4	35.55**	-0.86
19	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-5	61.67**	8.78
20	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-6	40.34**	0.18
21	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-7	26.66**	-22.33**
22	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-1	71.03**	15.22**
23	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-2	33.84**	-11.75*
24	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-3	46.26**	9.28
25	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-4	57.10**	14.90**
26	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-5	83.92**	23.75**
27	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-6	48.42**	5.95
28	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-7	17.11*	-22.78**
	S.E.(d) ±	0.848	0.98
	CD @ 5%	1.701	1.964

*, ** Significant at 5 and 1 per cent probability levels, respectively.

BP, SC indicates better parent and standard check LSFH-171, respectively

Table 4.3.7 Estimates of heterosis over better parent (BP) and standard check (SC) under individual and pooled over environments for seed yield per plant (g) in sunflower

Sr. No.	Crosses	Seed yield per plant (g)	
		Vanarasi (E ₃)	
		BP	SC
1	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-1	69.58**	0.65
2	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-2	76.95**	5.03
3	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-3	56.28**	-7.24
4	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-4	86.27**	10.56
5	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-5	53.81**	-8.71
6	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-6	63.53**	-2.94
7	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-7	96.09**	16.39
8	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-1	74.01**	3.28
9	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-2	55.52**	-7.69
10	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-3	134.61**	39.25**
11	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-4	90.65**	13.16
12	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-5	109.69**	24.46*
13	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-6	93.15**	14.64
14	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-7	70.47**	1.18
15	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-1	103.12**	20.56
16	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-2	52.28**	-9.62
17	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-3	88.26**	11.74
18	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-4	71.54**	1.81
19	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-5	121.34**	31.37**
20	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-6	79.46**	6.51
21	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-7	66.00**	-1.47
22	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-1	88.23**	11.72
23	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-2	64.66**	-2.27
24	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-3	101.01**	19.31
25	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-4	112.05**	25.86*
26	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-5	136.9**	40.61**
27	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-6	93.15**	14.64
28	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-7	62.46**	-3.57
	S.E.(d) ±	3.271	3.777
	CD @ 5%	6.558	7.573

*, ** Significant at 5 and 1 per cent probability levels, respectively.

BP, SC indicates better parent and standard check LSFH-171, respectively.

Table 4.3.8 Estimates of heterosis over better parent (BP) and standard check (SC) under individual and pooled over environments for seed volume weight (g/100 ml) in sunflower

Sr. No.	Crosses	Seed volume weight (g/100 ml)	
		Vanarasi (E ₃)	
		BP	SC
1	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-1	35.50**	-1.16
2	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-2	41.94**	0.63
3	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-3	15.66**	-7.68
4	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-4	41.27**	3.3
5	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-5	20.19**	-9.64*
6	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-6	36.15**	-3.48
7	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-7	46.85**	4.11
8	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-1	41.00**	2.86
9	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-2	28.29**	-7.68
10	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-3	42.06**	13.39**
11	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-4	41.39**	3.39
12	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-5	39.19**	4.64
13	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-6	45.16**	4.46
14	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-7	41.07**	1.52
15	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-1	49.94**	9.38*
16	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-2	49.71**	-7.77
17	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-3	31.66**	5.09
18	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-4	39.80**	2.23
19	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-5	42.16**	6.88
20	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-6	52.56**	6.25
21	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-7	49.28**	-7.23
22	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-1	46.17**	9.11*
23	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-2	27.03**	-5.18
24	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-3	30.54**	4.2
25	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-4	42.94**	6.7
26	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-5	51.19**	13.66**
27	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-6	38.16**	3.13
28	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-7	28.71**	-3.93
	S.E.(d) ±	1.46	1.685
	CD @ 5%	2.926	3.379

*, ** Significant at 5 and 1 per cent probability levels, respectively.

BP, SC indicates better parent and standard check LSFH-171, respectively.

Table 4.3.9 Estimates of heterosis over better parent (BP) and standard check (SC) under individual and pooled over environments for 100 grain weight (g) in sunflower

Sr. No.	Crosses	100 grain weight (g)	
		Vanarasi (E ₃)	
		BP	SC
1	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-1	27.91**	-4.62
2	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-2	41.13**	1.16
3	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-3	8.9	-8.09
4	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-4	39.06**	2.89
5	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-5	24.03**	-7.51
6	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-6	23.66**	-6.36
7	SVCMS-1 X SVSR-7	44.53**	6.94
8	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-1	25.00**	-1.73
9	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-2	15.44	-9.25
10	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-3	47.26**	24.28**
11	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-4	36.03**	6.94
12	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-5	46.32**	15.03*
13	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-6	36.03**	6.94
14	SVCMS-2 X SVSR-7	22.06**	-4.05
15	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-1	41.09**	5.2
16	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-2	24.19**	-10.98
17	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-3	28.77**	8.67
18	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-4	32.81**	-1.73
19	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-5	53.49**	14.45*
20	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-6	34.35**	1.73
21	SVCMS-3 X SVSR-7	21.87*	-9.83
22	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-1	43.41**	6.94
23	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-2	29.46**	-3.47
24	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-3	23.97**	4.62
25	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-4	50.39**	12.14
26	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-5	68.22**	25.43**
27	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-6	38.17**	4.62
28	SVCMS-4 X SVSR-7	22.48*	-8.67
	S.E.(d) ±	0.323	0.373
	CD @ 5%	0.648	0.749

*, ** Significant at 5 and 1 per cent probability levels, respectively.

BP, SC indicates better parent and standard check LSFH-171, respectively